

WHAT ARE THE VIEWS OF ACCEPTANCE LEVELS AND EFFECTIVE PHYSICAL LISTENING SKILLS OF MOTHERS WITH 6-YEAR-OLD CHILDREN?

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Abstract:

This research examined the views of mothers with 6-year-old children about their acceptance levels of the children and their effective physical listening skills. The study group of this research consisted of 32 mothers with 6-year-old children living in central districts of Konya-Turkey province. A semi-structured interview technique was used as the data collection method in the research. When the findings obtained from the research are examined, the views of the mothers on the levels of acceptance of their children, their effective physical listening skills, moments of listening without looking at the faces of their children and without establishing eye contact are placed in five categories. There are three categories concerning whether mothers' acceptance and tolerance towards their children increases. There are three categories concerning whether mothers' tolerance towards their children and behaviour decreases. The findings of the research are discussed in light of the related literature.

Keywords: mothers with children aged 6 years, acceptance, active physical listening

1. Introduction

Children need to have positive relationships with those who are responsible for their care (Önder & Gülay, 2007). For this reason, parental acceptance affects children's lifelong social and emotional development (Rohner, Kean, & Cournoyer, 1991). Parental acceptance affects a child's social life, and if a child thinks that their parents accept him/her, they can adapt themselves to social life more than children who think that they are rejected by their parents (Walters & Stinnett, 1971).

2. Contribution of this paper to the literature

- It is important that parents' acceptance levels of the children and their effective physical listening skills to be aware of their skills.

- As the study was qualitative, a more detailed conclusion was reached about the parents' views on the subject.
- It contributes to parents' ability to raise individuals with self-confident, healthy generations with developed communication skills.

Perceived acceptance or rejection forms the emotional dimension of interpersonal relationships, and this dimension may exist in all people because every person has more or less love from an attachment figure or from a person who is important to them (Khaleque & Rohner, 2012). According to parents, making children feel they are accepted is sometimes easier than showing it. Parents may show their acceptance of their children with facial expressions, movements, and other nonverbal expressions or bodily expressions (Zolten & Long, 2006: 2). In other words, a parent may express parental love in two ways: physically and verbally. Behaviours such as physically kissing, hugging, smiling, or pampering show that these are visible behaviours. Orally, love is expressed through telling children positive things, giving them compliments or admiring them (Rohner & Khaleque, 2002).

Parents' messages and forms of communication based on not accepting their children prevent healthy communication with their children and lead to the formation of communication barriers. The opposite kinds of communication strengthen the communication between mother and child. For example, in a study done by Ramsden and Hubbard (2002), acceptance of the child's negative feelings by the mother was found to have an indirect relationship with reducing the aggression affecting the child's emotional order. Parents who provide their children with much love, understanding and acceptance help to create an environment for open communication (Dönmezer, 1999).

People often confuse listening with hearing. Listening is analysing the sounds that come to the ear rather than recognising the meaning (Adair, 2016: 86). Gable (2003) states that the most important skill parents should acquire is listening to their children well when communicating with them. Paying attention so as to respond to the stimulus in order to understand the verbal messages correctly from a person who speaks or reads vocally is called listening (Demirel & Şahinel, 2006: 72, Özbay, 2005: 11, Sever, 2011: 10). Physical listening and physical attention, looking into the eyes of the person who is speaking, and silence are the conditions for being a good listener (Navaro, 2009: 132-134). Effective listening consists of stages such as expressing what the listeners hear with their own words; the listener is not just at the level of meaning but reflects the feelings behind the words of the speaker, reflecting both emotions and content through the listener's own expression (Cüceloğlu, 1995).

The basic principle in the process of interpersonal communication is to be able to accept people with their own specific qualifications. Acceptance is an indication of the value given to the interlocutor. The person who realises that he/she is accepted sincerely and as is by someone else feels free and starts to think about how to change. He/she can learn to solve his/her problems, his/her psychological health can improve, he/she designs how to be different, how to do more than he/she can; he/she becomes more productive, more creative; in short, he/she improves positively. Special skills are

required for acceptance. Many people see acceptance as a passive event. For them, this way of thinking is an inner behaviour or a feeling. Acceptance is inner, but it must be transmitted effectively, and it must be shown to be an impressive power for others. Parents especially should see their children as different individuals. They should accept them as they are, considering that they are free in their emotions, thoughts and behaviours (Baymur, 1993: 280; Gordon, 2001: 51-53; Çağdaş, 2012: 37).

Thus, self-confident, healthy generations with developed communication skills can grow up. From this point on, the purpose of this research is to examine the acceptance levels by mothers with 6-year-old children and what their views on effective physical listening skills directed at these children are. When this happens, communication between mother and child will become healthier, children who feel that they are being listened to and accepted can be individuals with high self-esteem, self-confidence, and healthy communication skills. To reach this objective, the following questions will be asked:

A. For Effective Physical Listening;

1. In what situations do you most listen to your children without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact?
2. What kind of reactions does your child give you when you listen without looking at your child's face and/or without establishing eye contact?
3. Have you thought what kind of messages you send them and what kind of emotions you make them feel when you listen to them without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact?
4. What do you feel when your mother, father, friends, or your partner listens to you without looking at your face and making eye contact while listening to you in your daily life?
5. What kind of clues does the eye contact you establish give you about the feelings, thoughts and behaviour of your children?

B. For Mother's Acceptance of Her Child;

1. In what situations does your tolerance increase more towards your children and their behaviour?
2. What kind of reactions do you give to the negative behaviour of your children when your tolerance is high?
3. In what situations does your tolerance decrease towards your children and their behaviour?
4. What kind of reactions do you give to your children's negative behaviour when your tolerance is low?
5. How do you tell your child that you do not accept his/her feelings and give him/her negative emotions?

3. Method

3.1 Research Model

A qualitative research technique was used in this study. Qualitative research produces knowledge to explain people's lifestyles, behaviours, social change and what meanings people attribute to events (see also Özdemir, 2010). Because of these properties, a qualitative method was preferred for this research.

3.2 Working Group

A purposive sampling method was used in this research. Purposive sampling allows for in-depth research by selecting rich situations in terms of information depending on the purpose of the study (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç-Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz, Demirel, 2008). If certain data sources in the population are believed to be the core of our problem, these elements will be selected in a controlled manner within the population (Arık, 1998: 266). The reason for choosing this sampling method is to obtain deeper and more detailed information about the acceptance and effective listening abilities of mothers with 6-year-old children. A specific criterion for selecting mothers for our purposeful sampling was determined. The maternal selection criterion for the working group was for mothers who have 6-year-old children group attending National Education-affiliated kindergartens located in the central districts of Konya. The working group consisted of 32 mothers. The age distribution of the mothers was as follows: 4 mothers between the ages of 25-30, 8 mothers between the ages of 31-35, 16 mothers between the ages of 36-40, and 4 mothers between the ages of 41-45. As for education level, there were 5 primary school graduate mothers, 11 secondary school graduate mothers, 14 high school graduate mothers and 2 university graduate mothers.

3.3 Semi-structured Interview Technique

A semi-structured interview technique was used as the data collection method in the data collection, and related literature was searched. Semi-structured interviews allow you to go into the ins and outs in the relevant area. Semi-structured interviews were preferred because of the ease of analysing the data obtained and the possibility of self-expression (Büyüköztürk et al., 2008).

In line with existing literature, we focused on the acceptance and effective listening skills of mothers with 6-year-old children. A semi-structured interview form consisting of questions was developed in order to determine mothers' views on acceptance and effective listening skills. To ensure the validity of the interview form, the interview form was given to five faculty members at Necmettin Erbakan University Turkey specialising in psychological counseling and guidance, and a semi-structured interview form was formed in line with the opinions of the lecturers. Then, pilot applications were made, and with adjustments, the interview forms were made ready to apply according to all these results. The applications were made by taking note of one of the two basic methods that were followed in recording the interview data in accordance with the interview technique (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005). During the

interviews with the mothers, voice recordings were not used. Giving a direct citation from the views of the mothers and explaining the results is important for validity.

3.4 Collecting the Data

Participation in the interviews was voluntary. An explanation for the interviews was prepared; the purpose of the research and how it would be carried out was clearly stated in the explanation. It was also emphasised that the identities of the participants in the interviews would be hidden. Written interview forms were used during the interviews. The interviews took approximately 40-45 minutes.

3.5 Analysis and Interpretation of the Data

A content analysis technique was applied to the collected data. The main goal in content analysis is to reach the concepts and relations that can explain the collected data. The basic procedure in content analysis is to organise and interpret similar data understandably by putting them together within the framework of specific concepts and themes. For this purpose, the collected data were first conceptualised; then, they were regulated logically according to emerging concepts; and accordingly, determinations of the themes explaining the data were made (Tavşancıl & Aslan, 2001; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005).

Qualitative data analysis consists of the processes of classification, i.e., dividing the data into clusters according to their similarities and differences; correlation, i.e., linking the data fragments and categories in the categories and subcategories with each other; and establishing connections, i.e., establishing links between existing categories and concepts within research objectives (See also Kuş, 2006:17). Interviewees' opinions were taken in semi-structured forms in writing. Each interview was numbered starting from one. Coding was done within the framework of the purpose and interview questions of the research. While coding, "Nvivo7" a computer-aided qualitative data analysis program, was utilised. Categories were used to analyse and compare various meanings in a category created at the lowest level. As a result of the opinions obtained from the related literature for these studies, the themes related to the acceptance levels and effective physical listening skills of mothers with 6-year-old children were determined. These themes are divided into subcategories. Model mother's views on each category were given.

4. Findings

Acceptance levels of mothers with 6-year-old children and their effective physical listening skills were analysed, and 10 themes-5 for effective physical listening and 5 for acceptance-were determined. These themes were then divided into categories. Discussions on each category were included. The themes, the categories related to the themes, the number of mothers who gave opinions on the categories, and the model mother's opinions are shown in Table 1 and Table 2 in detail.

Table 1: Opinions of Mothers with 6-year-old Children
towards Effective Physical Listening Skills

Themes	Categories	Number of Mothers Participating in Categories	Model Mothers' Views
1. Mothers' moments of listening to their children without looking at their face and establishing eye contact	While doing housework	13 Individuals	A17: When I am busy at home, while cleaning, doing kitchen work, washing dishes, ironing, when I am in a rush to cook.
	In Mother's Negative Mood	3 Individuals	A2: When I really do not want to listen to my child, when I'm nervous, when I'm bored.
	In Mother's Negative Physical Condition	2 Individuals	A32: When I am sick, tired and physically weak, when I feel serious discomfort.
	In Mother's Own Time	6 Individuals	A8: While reading a book, watching TV, playing games, doing handiwork.
	In Mother's Busy Business Life	8 Individuals	A6: When I have work, when I am very busy, and my child also tries to tell me something, I cannot establish eye contact.
2. The reactions of the children to their mothers when they listen to their children without looking at their faces, without establishing eye contact	Emotional Reactions	7 Individuals	A3: He/she gets angry, becomes irritated, gets mad.
	Physical Reactions	14 Individuals	A13: He/she turns my face towards himself/herself saying "Mother, please listen to me, please look at me," hangs on my arm, even says "Mom look at me, you do not even see", he/she sometimes nudges me hard and loud, then he/she gets ill-tempered, goes away slamming the door.
	Both Emotional and Physical Reactions	11 Individuals	A25: He/she gets angry, becomes irritated, he/she repeats what he/she says. He/she stomps his/her feet thinking he/she is not being listened to and yells "Will you please listen to me", yells "Mom! Look at my face!"
3. As to whether the mothers think of the messages they send to their children and the feelings they make them have while listening to their children without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact	Mother's Care About Child's Feelings	18 Individuals	A17: I did not use to think before, "What! Here, I am listening to you!" I used to shout. I saw that he/she was not wanted, ignored, got hurt, upset or even frustrated. That is why I care about him/her now.
	Mother's Disregarding	14 Individuals	A24: No, I think I'm uninterested. I think what I'm doing is wrong, but

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	for Child's Feelings		I am making the same mistakes in spite of myself.
4. What mothers feel when their own parents, their own friends or their partner listen to them without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact	Damage of Self-respect	20 Individuals	A8: I feel myself ignored, bad and worthless.
	Emotional Burnout	12 Individuals	A26: I get angry, I decide not to talk.
5. Clues that children give about their feelings, thoughts and behaviours as a result of the mothers' establishing eye contact in their communication with their children	Clue for gestures and gestures	21 Individuals	A17: Yes, he/she does. When he/she lies, his/her face goes red. He/she turns his/her eyes away. He/she has his/her eyes shine with joy when he/she is happy. Sometimes he/she looks another way when he/she lies. He/she drops his/her head.
	Emotional Clue	11 Individuals	A16: Yes, he/she does. I can understand his/her feelings that moment better. There is no need for further elaboration. Sadness, disappointment, anger, happiness, confusion; in short, I can understand many of his/her feelings.

4.1 When Mothers Listen to their children Without Looking at Their Faces and Without Establishing Eye Contact

In moments when mothers listen to their children without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact are examined, 5 categories appear. There are 13 mothers in the doing housework category, 3 in the mother's negative mood category, 2 in the mother's negative physical condition category, 6 in the mother's own time category and 8 in the mother's busy business life category.

4.2 Reactions of Children to Their Mothers When They Listen to the Children without Looking at Their Faces and Without Establishing Eye Contact

In the reactions of children to their mothers when they listen to the children without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact is examined, 3 categories appear. There are 7 mothers in the emotional reactions category, 14 in the physical reactions category, and 11 in the both emotional and physical reactions category.

4.3 Whether the Mothers Think of the Messages They Send to Their Children and the Feelings They Make Them Have While Listening to Their Children without Looking at Their Faces and Without Establishing Eye Contact

When whether the mothers think of the messages, they send to their children and the feelings they make them have while listening to their children without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact is examined, 2 categories appear. There are

18 mothers in the category of giving importance to the feelings of the child and 14 in the category of not giving importance to the feelings of the child.

4.4 What Mothers Feel When Their Own Parents, Their Own Friends or Their Partner Listen to Them without Looking at Their Faces and Without Establishing Eye Contact

When what mothers feel when their own parents, their own friends or their partner listen to them without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact is examined, 2 categories appear. There are 20 mothers in the category of damage to self-respect and 12 in the emotional burnout category.

4.5 Clues that Children Have about Their Feelings, Thoughts and Behaviours as a result of The Mothers' Establishing Eye Contact in Their Communication with Their Children

When clues that children have about their feelings, thoughts and behaviours as a result of the mothers' establishing eye contact in their communication with their children are examined, 2 categories appear. There are 21 mothers in the clue from gestures category and 11 mothers in the emotional clue category.

Table 2: Opinions of Mothers with 6-year-old Children towards Levels of Acceptance

Themes	Categories	Number of Mothers Participating in Categories	Model Mothers' Views
1. The moments when mothers' tolerance increases to their children and to their behaviours	Mother's being positive in the emotional aspect	18 Individuals	A10: When I am happy, cheerful, when my morale is high, when I am not angry.
	Mother's being positive in the physical aspect	8 Individuals	A26: When I am not sick, when my health is good.
	Mother's business intensity is low	6 Individuals	A31: When they do what we say, when everything is alright.
2. The reactions of the mothers to their children's negative behaviours during the days when their tolerance is high.	Authoritarian and Repressive attitude	5 Individuals	A31: I warn them, I forewarn them, I put pressure on them. I raise my voice, I cannot tolerate the slightest misbehaviour. I can be distressing and unkind to them.
	Overprotective attitude	3 Individuals	A21: I address all my child's requests and behaviours.
	Tolerant permissive attitude	8 Individuals	A30: It'd be better if you hadn't done that, but I can say don't worry.
	Uninterested attitude	3 Individuals	A9: I pretend not to see it. I don't care about it at all if I don't have to.
	Democratic attitude	13 Individuals	A28: By establishing a more relaxed dialogue in a calm and positive way, I am trying to

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			explain how it should be and why his/her negative behaviours are wrong.
3. The moments when mothers' tolerance of their children and their behaviours decreases	Mother's being negative in the emotional aspect	15 Individuals	A11: When I'm nervous and unhappy, everything gets out of hand.
	Mother's being negative in the physical aspect	9 Individuals	A28: When I have a headache, when I feel tired due to tiring housework, when I feel discomfort.
	The increase in the work intensity of the mother	8 Individuals	A16: When I have a stressful, heavy, hard day.
4. The reactions of the mothers to their children's negative behaviours during the days when their tolerance is low.	Physical reactions	22 Individuals	A24: I raise my voice, I shout, I often use the word "No!" I can stubbornly refuse to do what my child says. I even commit violence if necessary.
	Emotional reactions	10 Individuals	A2: I get angry, I become irritated, I get mad.
5. The ways of expressing their feelings to their children, which make them feel negative, and which are not accepted by mothers.	Using eye contact	6 Individuals	A28: I come to the same level with my child looking at his/her eyes and I put my hand on his/her shoulder.
	Verbal expression	23 Individuals	A30: I say "My little one, I have a toothache today, please will you play nicely" or "I think in this way, what do you think."
	By building empathy	5 Individuals	A5: I explain without hurting him/her, without offending him/her considering that he/she also has feelings.

4.6 The Moments When Mothers' Tolerance Increases to Their Children and to Their Behaviours

When the mothers' tolerance increases to their children and to their behaviours are examined, 3 categories appear. There are 18 mothers in the mother's being emotionally positive category, 8 in the mother's being physically positive category and 6 in the mother's business intensity is low category.

4.7 Reactions of Mothers When Their Tolerance is High to Their Children and to Their Behaviours

When the reactions of mothers when their tolerance is high to their children and to their behaviours are examined, 5 categories appear. There are 5 mothers in the authoritarian and repressive attitude category, 3 in the overprotective attitude category, 8 in the

tolerant permissive attitude category, 3 in the uninterested attitude category and 13 in the democratic attitude category.

4.8 The Moments When Mothers' Tolerance of Their Children and Their Behaviours Decreases

When the mothers' tolerance decreases to their children and their behaviours is examined, 3 categories appear. There are 9 mothers in the mother's being emotionally negative category, 9 in the mother's being physically negative category and 8 in the category of increase in the work intensity of the mother.

4.9 The Reaction of Mothers to The Negative Behaviours of Their Children When Their Tolerance is Low

When the reaction of mothers to the negative behaviours of their children when their tolerance is low is examined, 2 categories appear. There are 22 mothers in the physical reactions category and 10 in the emotional reactions category.

4.10 The Ways of Expressing Their Feelings to Their Children, Which Make Them Feel Negative, and Which Are Not Accepted by Mothers

When the ways of expressing their feelings to their children, which make them feel negative, and which are not accepted by mothers are examined, 3 categories appear. There are 6 mothers in the category using eye contact, 23 in the verbal expression category and 5 in the building empathy category.

5. Discussion

When the moments when mothers listen to their children without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact are examined, 5 categories appear. There are 13 mothers in the category of doing house work, 3 in the mother's negative mood category, 2 in the mother's negative physical condition category, 6 in the mother's own time category, 8 in the mother's busy business life category.

When these findings are taken into consideration, it seems that the mothers listen to their children without looking at their faces and establishing eye contact most while doing housework. The mother does not accept many behaviours of her child, she reacts in the case of having a misfortune at home on a difficult day, and she rushes to do things, but the wheels have come off (Navaro, 1999: 134; Tayfun, 2009: 176). Mothers spend considerable time with housework during the day. It is important to do two tasks at once for the mother who has to address both the children and the housework. Of course, this influences the mother's priorities, and the mother, who is in a hurry to catch up on things, can harm her communication with her child by placing the child on the second priority.

When the reactions of children to their mothers when they listen to the children without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact are examined, 3 categories appear. There are 7 mothers in the emotional reactions category, 14 in the

physical reactions category and 11 in the both emotional and physical reactions category.

When these findings are taken into consideration, it seems that the reactions of the children to their mothers are mostly physical. A light stroke on the shoulder, a hug, a gentle hand wringing or other sensual contact arouses a stronger love than spoken words (Sears & Sears, 2004: 319). Dalsgaard et al. (2006) stated that physical contact is very important for the communication of parents with their children. Just as the parents convey their love better physically, the child who understands that he/she is not listened to can indicate his/her discomfort primarily physically and can try to attract the mother's attention by reacting physically.

When whether the mothers think of the messages, they send to their children and the feelings they make them have while listening to their children without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact is examined, 2 categories appear. There are 18 mothers in the category of giving importance to the feelings of the child and 14 in the category of not giving importance to the feelings of the child.

When these findings are taken into account, it is seen that there is a maximum of 18 mothers in the category of giving importance to the emotions of the child. Communication with his/her mother is of great importance in the child's world. Successful communication can be established between mother and child by transferring the child's feelings to his/her mother and the mother's accepting them (Yavuzer, 1999: 116). Mothers generally care about the feelings of their children. However, sometimes, unwittingly, feelings can lose importance during communication, and only behavioural reactions can come to the forefront.

When what mothers feel when their own parents, their own friends or their partner listen to them without looking at their faces and without establishing eye contact is examined, 2 categories appear. There are 20 mothers in the category of damage of self-respect and 12 in the emotional burnout category.

When these findings are taken into consideration, it is seen that the mothers give opinions the most in the category of damage of self-respect. Colwell and Hart (2006) observed children's relationships with their mothers. According to the obtained results, the skills of understanding emotion belonging to the children who establish good quality relationships with their mothers were observed to be more developed. In another study, it was shown that parents' acceptance and rejection levels for pre-school children (5-6 years) can affect their social relations (Gülay, 2011).

When clues that children give about their feelings, thoughts and behaviours as a result of the mothers' establishing eye contact in their communication with their children are examined, 2 categories appear. There are 21 mothers in the clue for gestures and gestures category and 11 in the emotional clue category.

When these findings are taken into account, it is seen that when mothers establish eye contact with their children, they communicate with their children the most by giving meaning to their gestures and mimics. At this point, body language is at the forefront. Gestures and mimicry in nonverbal communication also tell us a lot. Body language; gestures and mimics made with facial expressions, head, arms, hands and the

other elements of the body; and non-verbal communication elements such as body posture, eye contact, physical contact, nearness, distance, image, etc. are the factors that facilitate communication (Mısırlı, 2007: 55; Stanton, 2004: 13; Voltan-Acar, 2012: 111). From this point of view, it is understandable that children reveal their feelings through their gestures and mimicry.

When the moments when mothers' tolerance of their children and their children's behaviours increases are examined, 3 categories appear. There are 18 mothers in the mother's being emotionally positive category, 8 in mother's being physically positive category and 6 in mother's business intensity is low category.

When these findings are taken into consideration, it is seen that the moments in which mothers' tolerance increases the most are the moments when the mother is emotionally positive. Wilson and Durbin (2012) linked parents' positive and negative feelings with their ability to respond to their children in their work; they reached the conclusion that parents can respond positively to their child when they have positive feelings. It is more likely that a happy, psychologically healthy, self-confident mother communicates with her child more receptively, and this increases the quality of the communication.

When the reactions of mothers to their children and their behaviours when their tolerance is high are examined, 5 categories appear. There are 5 mothers in the authoritarian and repressive attitude category, 3 in the overprotective attitude category, 8 in the tolerant and permissive attitude category, 3 in the uninterested attitude category and 13 in the democratic attitude category. When these findings are examined, it is seen that mothers exhibit the democratic attitude the most. It was found that as the supportive mother attitude increases in coping with the negative emotions of the child, the child's ability to regulate his/her feelings also increased (Kurbet, 2010). On the other hand, according to Gövsa (1998), the judgemental parent's attitude affects the child's speech and causes communication disorder. The child's fear of his ideas not being liked and listened to is common in families who are condemning because of repressive and meaningless talk. From this point of view, a more democratic attitude of mothers may be a feature that can positively influence communication on days when their tolerance is high.

When the moments when mothers' tolerance of their children and their behaviours decreases are examined, 3 categories appear. There are 15 mothers in the mother's being emotionally negative category, 9 in the mother's being physically negative and 8 in the increase in the work intensity of the mother category. When these findings are examined, it seems that the mothers' tolerance towards their children and their behaviours decreases the most are the moments in which they are emotionally negative. When the mother feels happy, does not have any health problems, does not have urgent work to finish, does not argue with her husband, or has a good day with a friend, she easily accepts many behaviours of her child and ignores even the behaviours she generally gets angry about. At such times, the mother's acceptance line is low (Navaro, 1999: 134; Çağdaş, 2012: 38). On the other hand, when the mother is

emotionally negative, a decreased tolerance towards her children and their behaviours may be expected.

When the mothers' reactions to the negative behaviours of their children when their tolerance is low are examined, 2 categories appear. There are 22 mothers in the physical reactions category and 10 in the emotional reactions category. When these findings are examined, it is seen that mothers have the most physical reaction to the negative behaviours of their children when their tolerance is low. Body language, which we can call nonverbal communication, is mostly an unconscious and natural expression of our feelings (Adair, 2016: 20-21). Stephenson and Dowrick (2005) investigated parents' ability to communicate with their children in order to demonstrate that their responsibilities in the development of their children's communication skills played a major role. According to the results obtained, hand and arm movements and voices were seen as the most tools in communication. As this study shows, mothers are most likely to respond physically to their children's negative behaviour.

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Cagla Girgin-Buyukbayraktar
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